

Decision theory and climate policy

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Climate science contributes to decision making in matters of climate policy by providing estimates of the possible impacts of human activities (mainly due to greenhouse gas emissions but also large scale exploitation of land and water resources) on the climate and, the other way round, of the possible impacts of climate change on societies.

Possible impacts (either of human activities on the climate or the other way round) are called scenarios and the main methodology for generating scenarios in climate science is developing computer-based models and performing model simulations.

While climate models can, up to a certain extent, be validated on the basis of indirect observations of past climates (paleo-climatology) and of a growing amount of direct observations and the (conditional) probabilities of different climate change scenarios (for given anthropogenic forcings) can be estimated, assessing the feedback of climate change on societies is more controversial and requires more interdisciplinary efforts.

Because of this asymmetry, climate science has been so far incapable of providing advice on matters of climate policy that is accountable: decision makers do not precisely know what kind of guarantees they can expect from implementing the advice received.

Integrated assessment models (IAMs) of climate change of the kind discussed in (Nordhaus 2018) have been successfully applied to inform decision making but they have also been criticized, mainly because of three reasons: 1) their lack of predictive capability; 2) their reliance on cost-benefit analysis and marginality assumptions and 3) their focus on deterministic sequential decision problems.

While it is true that relevant IAM outputs (for example a social price of carbon) critically depend on the values of model parameters (climate sensitivity, discount factors) that can hardly be estimated reliably (Pindyck 2017), the lack of predictive capability is not the main reason of concern: IAMs are finally not applied for predicting the impacts of climate change on societies but rather for comparing and understanding such impacts.

The reliance of IAMs on marginality (Sharpe and Nijssse 2021) assumptions, cost-benefit analysis and deterministic sequential decision problems, however, are more concerning limitations: cost-benefit analysis requires monetizing the possible impacts of climate change on societies but we do not know how to fairly price these impacts. And the fact that we also do not know how to reliably attach probabilities to impacts of climate change should not be a justification for falsely assuming them to be known with certainty!

More realistic approaches towards rationalizing climate decisions on GHG emissions attempt at

accounting for multi-objective notions of optimality (Carlino et al. 2020) in optimal control or for the impact of uncertainties, e.g. on the inertia of legislations and the capability of (global!) decision makers to actually implement decisions (Botta, Jansson, and Ionescu 2018) and on solar radiation management options (Moreno-Cruz and Keith 2012), (Helwegen et al. 2019).

While these approaches can help understanding how uncertainty and the attitude of decision makers towards uncertainties (risk neutral, risk averse, etc.) affect “best” global decisions and can also help clarify the trade-offs made when defining what is “best”, they do not tackle the problem of how independent decision makers in a competitive environment can actually coordinate and agree to implement such decisions.

Answering this question requires integrating, among others, optimal control theory, game theory, political science, climate economics and formal methods and is a relatively new research area (Heitzig, Lessmann, and Zou 2011), (Heitzig 2012).

In a nutshell: decision theory (or, better, decision theories) play a crucial role for accountable, pragmatic decision making in matters of climate policies.

At this point, however, their most valuable contribution is perhaps to make clear (to policy advisors, decision makers and, by large, to the civil society), the assumptions implicit in rationalizing decision making in matters of climate policy and the fact that best decisions crucially depend on what we are set to achieve on which time scale, on our attitude with respect to risk and on uncertainties that we can hardly estimate, let apart avoid.

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